

Exchange Rate Volatility and its Implications for Economic Growth in Developing Economies —A Case Study of Nigeria Within 1993 to 2023

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Abstract

Exchange rate volatility signifies the movement of exchange rate of countries which is an important macroeconomic phenomenon that affects trade competitiveness, inflation, investment flows and long-run growth of countries. This paper examines the impact of exchange rate fluctuation on the economic growth of Nigeria within 1993 to 2023. The study examined the analysed key macroeconomic variables including foreign direct investment (FDI), crude oil prices, export value, import value, inflation rate, and electricity distribution. The analysis employed descriptive statistics, Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) to determine unit root tests, Johansen cointegration techniques to establish the relationship between the variables in the study, and a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to capture both long-run equilibrium relationships and short-run adjustment dynamics.

Findings suggest that the generalized autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity - based measure of nominal and real exchange rate volatility has a negative impact on economic growth, because the country's dependent mostly on foreign exchange from oil export. Also, the effect of exchange rate volatility depends on the crude oil price movement, exchange rate regimes and macroeconomic policies implemented by the government since Nigeria is majorly a crude oil export nation.

For Nigeria to enjoy a stable exchange rate it has to address the challenges in its transmission channels, to avoid short-run shocks which hinders the realization of long-run economic potential through export diversification, infrastructure development, and policies that attract sustainable FDI

for both local consumption and export as well as an assured positive economic growth it is necessary the government diversify the economy to encourage multi-culture foreign exchange inflow nation, where several sectors would earn steady export proceeds from her products and services.

Keywords: Exchange rate volatility, inflation rate, Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), export proceeds, diversification, long run equilibrium, macroeconomic variables and multi-cultural foreign exchange rate.

1.0 Introduction

The relationship between exchange rate movements and macroeconomic performance has been at the centre of economic discourse for decades. Since the advent of trade liberalisation policy developing economies has suffered from exchange rate volatility which has impacted the economies both positively and negatively. Part of the negative influence to Foreign exchange volatility suffered by developing countries is due to the unsteady interchange of goods, services and payments between countries. This results to the unsteady or unpredictable movements in a currency's value for countries involved the processes. Hence, majority of the

developing countries have been exposed to sharp exchange rate fluctuations. This situation has attracted the attention of economists and some of the previous research that focused on the effects of exchange rate volatility on trade inflows are Umeaduma, C. M. G., & Dugbartey, A. N. (2023)., Wong (2017), Karemera et al. (2015). The debate is further heightened with countries move to implementing a floating exchange rate regime, the advent of the liberalisation of the financial markets in the 1980s and the recent global economic crisis affecting economic growth. To this end we will agree that exchange rate is an important macroeconomic variable used as parameter for determining international competitiveness of between countries as such this indicate that the lower the currency value the stronger the currency compared to the competing currency. It becomes necessary to distinguish between the real exchange rate and nominal exchange rate of currencies. The Nominal exchange rate (NER) is a monetary concept, that measures the relative price of the two moneys or currencies e.g Naira in relation to U.S dollar. While Real exchange rate (RER) is being regarded as real concept that measure the relative price of two tradeable goods (exports and imports) in relation to non-tradeable goods (goods and services produced and consumed). However, Exchange rate system includes set of rules, arrangement and institutions under which nations effect payments among themselves. This mechanism or system is controlled by the law of demand and supply in foreign exchange market where by the variables that influence the exchange rate includes country's exports, imports and the economic structure and policies (McKinnon, R. I. 1996).

There were several studies carried out under different control variables and in a different environment to examine exchange rate volatility and its effect on economic growth with varying results (Eriş & Ulaşan, (2013); Wong, (2017)). However, these varying results between exchange rate volatility and economic growth may be attributed to country-specific factors such as the level of financial markets development, human capital development, governance and institutional structures. (Musyoki, Pokhariyal & Pundo ,(2012)).

High level of exchange rate volatility can create uncertainties that would disrupt the smooth functioning of the financial market and other economic activities, thereby causing reduced international trade activities; drop in investment and result to unfair competition that could give undue advantage to foreign firms in terms of product pricing.

The objective of this paper is to use the Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (GARCH) to model exchange rate volatility and the system Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) model to examine the effect of exchange rate volatility on economic growth in Nigeria and the Implication on the economic growth of the country within 1993 to 2023.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the literature review on the relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth. Section 3 describes the data set and the econometric methodology used. While Section 4 reports the empirical results of the paper, the final section conclusion and recommendations.

1.1 Problem Statement

Over several decades Nigeria has operated different foreign exchange regimes based on different macroeconomic policies implemented by different government but has however always been struggling with foreign exchange volatility which has generated mixed effect on the economic growth of the country, and this has created the cause of worry for researchers, economist, academicians alike. As such also created the gap necessary for this research study in order to carefully study the cause of this exchange rate volatility and how this affects the economic growth of the country in terms of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the country, export rate, import rate, inflation rate as well as infrastructural development of the

country within the periods of 1993 to 2023, since this period cover several foreign exchange regimes that has existed in the country.

1.2 Significance of the Study

The importance of this research study Is to review the empirical literature on foreign exchange volatility and to explore the effects of foreign exchange volatility on the economic growth of developing economies, specifically for Nigeria. Secondly, to study the causes of foreign exchange volatility in the country and offer relevant policy findings that can guide government strategies towards achieving stable foreign exchange regime in Nigeria. Thirdly, the study seeks to provide framework to assess improved foreign exchange policies align with Nigeria's long-term development goals, especially in the context of the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) and other international bodies. Finally, to serve as a reference point for academics, policymakers, and development practitioners seeking to understand the complexities of foreign exchange mechanism for economic trade-growth

1.3 Limitation and Scope of the Study

The period covered by this research study is from 1993 to 2023 and the research study focuses on the impact of foreign exchange volatility on the economic growth of developing nations specifically Nigeria, using indicators such as GDP growth rate, annual export value, exchange rate in dollars, the inflation rate of the country, annual import values and infrastructural development of the country. However, some of the limitations during the cause of the study are data availability and reliability of the social and environmental indicators. Also, to isolate the effects of one foreign exchange trade regime from other and comparing the economic policies indicators could link with each could be very difficult, given the interconnected nature of macroeconomic variables. Despite these constraints, the study maintains robust econometric techniques to ensure credible results.

2.0 Literature Review

Foreign exchange volatility can influence trade, investment, inflation, capital flows, and ultimately economic growth and welfare of a country. The empirical literature, however, reports heterogeneous results that depend on the objective of the research work, the country, the measure of volatility, and the econometric approach. Important conceptual and empirical contributions that frame this literature include Mundell's work of 1961 on the role of exchange rates in macro adjustment, the "fear of floating" literature (Calvo & Reinhart), which may be inimical to economic growth and cross-country empirical analyses of exchange-rate regimes and performance.

In furtherance to these several other overlapping theories explain how Foreign exchange volatility and its effect on economic outcomes; such as Edwards and Levy-Yeyati, (2005) show that exchange rate volatility allows absorbing external shocks by providing greater adaptive capacity while avoiding the persistent and economically expensive adjustment processes. Cerra et al. (2013) and Furceri and Zdzienicka (2011) conclude that during episodes of financial crises, countries with a flexible exchange rate experience lower production losses than fixed exchange rate countries. Another argument in favor of greater exchange rate flexibility/volatility is the monetary policy autonomy and the constraints of credibility and discipline imposed by the exchange rate regime (Mundell 1963, Dornbusch and Giovannini 1990). Indeed, flexible exchange rate regimes encourage an autonomous monetary policy in the presence of strong international capital mobility and thus, offer the possibility of stabilizing the domestic economy.

In Nigeria, Akpan & Atan (2012) furthered the study on this issue using the GMM to investigate the effects of exchange rate movements on economic growth in Nigeria. They argued that there was no evidence to suggest a strong direct link between exchange rate and output growth. Instead, monetary variables have been responsible for Nigeria economic growth. In 2015 Apollos, Emmanuel & Olusegun adopted the OLS technique and data for the period 1986-2013 to investigate the relationship between the GDP and exchange rate, imports, exports and the inflation rate in Nigeria. The result of their study revealed a significant positive relationship between the GDP and other explanatory variables like the exchange rate and exports. In a related study, Isola, Oluwafunke, Victor, & Asaleye (2016) employed the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to investigate the linkage between exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria from 2003-2013 and the results indicate that there is no relationship between the variables in the long run. One concern with some of the studies that used the OLS model is that they failed to account for the panel effects of the data used and the issue with the endogeneity of the variables in the study. Other studies have empirically examined the relationship between exchange rate volatility and the key determinants of economic growth, namely, international trade, investment, and employment. In this context, Vieira and MacDonald (2016) focus on the effects of the real effective exchange rate volatility on export flows in 106 developed and emerging countries between 2000 and 2011 and conclude the existence of a negative link between the two variables. Also in 2016 Pino et al. check the impact of the exchange rate volatility on exports in six Asian economies during the period of 1974~2011 and their empirical investigation reveals that exchange rate volatility has a harmful impact on exports, particularly in the long-run. Generally, the overview of exchange rate volatility and impact on economic growth of a country is of both sides depending on the country's developmental state, but however, flexible exchange rate is better for developing economies due to the domestic market adaptability potential.

2.1 History of Foreign Exchange in Nigeria

Nigeria has suffered several exchange rate regimes in order to stabilise the economy. The exchange rate plays a vital role in the prices of goods and services economically, allocation of resources and investment decisions. Since the mid-1980, the country moved from the fixed regimes and adopted the flexible exchange rate regimes though with periodic intervention by the regulatory authorities. In the opinion of Okoroafor & Adeniji (2017), no exchange rate could be allowed to float completely or be determined by the market forces without the periodic intervention of the regulatory authority in the bid to achieve some strategic objective of macroeconomic stability and growth. Following the creation of the Nigeria entity as an independent nation in 1960, the exchange rate policy has undergone a several transformation as part of the effort of the government to position the economy on the path of growth. For instance, between 1960 and August 1986, Nigeria adopted the direct exchange rate control mechanism to manage foreign exchange rate along with macroeconomic variables in order to stabilize the economy and stimulate growth. This system of direct exchange rate control was possible because of the boom in the prices of crude oil and rise in prices of agricultural produce at the market. However, the 1982 there was foreign exchange crisis that increased the demand for foreign exchange at that time the supply dwindled due to a drop in foreign earnings, this necessitated the exchange rate controls mechanism and resulted to the development of parallel foreign exchange markets to stabilise the economy. During this period, particularly between 1981 and 1986, the Naira depreciated against the dollar from N0.61 to N2.02. Since then Nigeria adopted the Structural Adjustment Policy (SAP) in 1986, with the introduction of different foreign exchange markets, such as the introduction of the Second-tier Foreign Exchange Market (SFEM) in 1986 and the Unified Official Market

(UOM) in 1987 to balance the economy. However, in 1990, the Naira depreciated further to N7.90. To stabilise the exchange rate, the government further introduced another foreign exchange rate reform and pegged the Naira exchange rate against the Dollar at N21.89 in 1994. The failure of that reform further made the government liberalise the Foreign Exchange Market in 1995 with the introduction of the Autonomous Foreign Exchange Market (AFEM). The foreign market was further liberalised and the Inter-bank Foreign Exchange Market (IFEM) was introduced in October 1999. During this same period, the Naira continue to deregulate as the exchange rate became N86.32 against the dollar. Furthermore, due to the high demand for foreign exchange and the consistent drop in the country foreign reserve, the government in 2002 deregulated the foreign exchange market and introduced the Dutch Auction System (DAS). During this period, the Naira to dollar traded for N120.97 in 2002 and N135.5 in 2004. Meanwhile, a reform exchange regime called the Wholesale Dutch Auction System (WDAS) was introduced in 2006. Interestingly, the government's efforts to stabilise the exchange rate paid off when the Naira appreciated to N132.15 in 2005 and N118.57 in 2008. However, this period was short-lived due to the global financial crisis which made the Naira depreciate to N150.01 against the dollar in 2009. The government's attempts to manage the exchange rate were aimed at finding an enduring solution to the foreign exchange crisis in the country, however, enjoyed some good foreign exchange earnings, particularly from oil revenue. Nevertheless, the actions of the present civilian administration again derailed the whole importance effort due to the poor policies implementation and corruption. For instance, between the middle of 2015 when the present administration led by President Muhammadu Buhari came into power and the second quarter of 2017, the domestic economy witnessed a serious adversity in the exchange rate volatility against the US dollar. The business environment suffered inconsistencies in government policies and this resulted to steady withdrawal of foreign currencies from the economy by foreign investors due to the uncertainty of the future of Nigeria economy. This poor policy situation, coupled with the fall in foreign inflows from oil revenue, created urge fall in foreign currencies inflow into the country. To address this imbalance, the government embarked on the devaluation of the Naira against the dollar and the exchange rate moved from N180 in mid-2015 to N254 in 2016 and N450 in 2017 as the official rate and Naira continued to depreciate until date, presently Naira exchanges for about N1,400 to a dollar

2.2 Exchange Rate Volatility

It is important to mention that there is no consensus on the adequate measure of volatility. The first issue refers to the choice of the exchange rate. Existing empirical studies do not offer consensual criteria regarding the use of nominal or real exchange rates. For instance, Servén (2003) computes the volatility of the real exchange rate which depends on the fluctuations of nominal exchange rate and prices. In contrast, according to Vanelle (2001), the nominal exchange rate is preferred because the real exchange rate incorporates price fluctuations, which represents another type of uncertainty for private agents. Finally, some studies suggest that the use of nominal or real exchange rates does not significantly affect the obtained results. In addition, it has been shown that real and nominal exchange rates have evolved in highly correlated fashion in the presence of floating exchange rate regimes, which explains the non-sensitivity of results regarding the used exchange rate proxy. The second issue is related to the choice of the volatility measure (Dell'Araccia 1999). The presence of multiple measures of volatility partly explains the ambiguous effects of exchange rate volatility on economic growth. Most empirical studies on the subject essentially make use of two measures. The first measure is based on the historical volatility and focuses on dispersion indicators such as the standard deviation and the coefficient of variation (Kenen and Rodrick 1986, Dell'Araccia 1999). However, historical volatility does not take into

account the exchange rate uncertainty, which represents the unforeseen share of exchange rate fluctuations. It would be better, therefore, to use the concept of conditional volatility as measured by the GARCH model developed by Bollerslev (1986). It is worth noting that most studies employ conditional volatility measures. Moreover, some show that exchange rate time series do not exhibit Gaussian behavior (Atlan et al. 1992) and thus, criticize the use of the standard deviation and the coefficient of variation.

The current paper measures exchange rate volatility based on the GARCH conditional variance using the following two equations:

$$ext = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i ext_{-i} + \varepsilon_t \text{ ----- (1)}$$

$$hmt = 2mt = \lambda_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \lambda_0 \varepsilon_{2t-1} + \mu_0 2t_{-i} \text{ -----(2)}$$

where ext and hmt denote the logarithm of nominal and real exchange rates and the conditional variance, respectively. The latter represents our monthly exchange rate volatility. The construction of the monthly exchange rate volatility indices using the GARCH (1,1) model is based on the estimation of Equations (1) and (2). The empirical analysis is carried out for 45 developing economies during the period 1985 to 2015. Monthly real and nominal effective exchange rates are extracted from the International Financial Statistics database of the International Monetary Fund. By estimating Equations (1) and (2) for each country, we obtain monthly exchange rate volatility time series. Figures 1 and 2 plot the evolution of monthly nominal and real exchange rate volatility by country (hmt).

Finally, we compute the annual exchange rate volatility as follows:

$$vex_t = 1/12 \times (hm_1 + hm_2 + \dots + hm_{12}) \text{ ----- (3)}$$

However, to estimate the foreign exchange volatility against economic growth the following model as equation (4) is applied

$$y_{it} = \alpha + \beta y_{it-1} + \phi vex_{it} + \delta' X_{it} + \mu_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{it} \text{ ----- (4)}$$

where

y_{it} = the logarithm of real per capita GDP

βy_{it} = lagged logarithm of real per capita GDP

α = the matrix of control variables

ϕvex_{it} = the conditional exchange rates volatility of X_{it}

$\delta' X_{it}$ = is a matrix of control variables

μ_i , λ_t and ε_{it} = the country-specific effects, the time specific effect, and the error term respectively

3.0 Research Methodology

This section deals with the procedure through which data for the research work is collected and the various analysis technique used for the processes are applied. The secondary data is collected from Central Bank Nigeria (CBN) annual reports, National Bureau Statistics (NBS) annual report, world bank quarterly reports and United Nation Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD). A complete description of the research design, data collection instruments utilised to achieved the research objective are elaborated carefully under this section.

3.1 Research Design

For this research study, the chosen research design is the ex-post facto research design. The selected research design is to use systematic method where the researcher cannot manipulate data collected due to its occurrence as it is an annual report published by reputable organ of government in Nigeria and internationally.

3.2 Justification of Methodology

The secondary data to be used in the research study will be on the economic indexes of Nigeria within the period of study which is from 1993 to 2023. Furthermore, it was chosen over other possible alternatives due to its accessibility and reliability after due considerable analysis and verification of the data collection.

3.3 Data Sources and Collection Instrument

The research Secondary data span from 1993 to 2023 extracted from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, National Bureau of Statistics Annual reports, WDI Annual Report and related research studies reports. The secondary data collected include; the Total Foreign Direct investment (TFDI), the contribution to the Nigerian Total Gross Domestic Product (TGDP) which serve as a proxy for economic growth of the country, the country's yearly Import value, Nigeria yearly export value, the average yearly exchange rate, average annual inflation rate and average electricity distribution. The choice of the secondary data is informed by the fact that data cannot be obtained through the primary source because they have to be collected over a longer period. The data were analysed using the descriptive analysis to identify the frequency distributions, means, and standard deviations. Regression analysis was also employed in determining the magnitude and direction of impact on the economic growth of the country. The trend of the data collected are also related to the existing policies implemented within the said periods, so as to be able to understand the effect of the policies and possible other factors. The variables used in the study include:

- o Total Annual Gross Domestic Products(TGDP)
- o Total Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflows
- o Average annual exchange rate in dollars (Fx)
- o Average annual inflation rate (Infl)
- o Export value (Expt) — annual export value in US dollar
- o Import value (Impt) — annual import value
- o Electricity Distribution (INFR) — annual average infrastructural development

3.4 Technique for Data Analysis

The study will be considering time series data and as such the following time series econometric procedure allows for distinguishing between short-run fluctuations and long-run relationships between the stated variables which enable us to achieve some of the objectives of the study using E-views 12 software or SPSS software to run the following tests;

1. **Descriptive Statistics Test:** This is for getting or measure the central tendency of values derived from data collection. **Examples are** Mean, median, mode, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis to summarise the data and detect outliers.
2. **Stationarity Test:** This is tests to determine the order of integration of the variables. It is also to investigate whether the data series has unit root or not, to prevent spurious regression results, a common problem with non-stationary macroeconomic data. The Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) and Phillips–Perron (PP) are used to examine the stationarity of the data series. Where the data series is found to be nonstationary, then a further test for stationarity is conducted in the first difference for each of the variables.
3. **Cointegration Test:** Johansen cointegration test to examine the presence of a long-run equilibrium relationship between variables that determine or effect exchange rate volatility on economic development of a developing economy such as Nigeria. Some of the parameters to check during evaluation are Trace statistics and the critical values of the test results. If cointegration is confirmed, a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) will be used to estimate both long-run coefficients and short-run adjustments.
4. **Granger Causality Test:** To investigate whether one or more variable(s) affect others and also assess the direction of causality if the relationship is positive or negative between variables that control or determine exchange rate volatility in a developing economy

such as Nigeria. However, the natural phenomenon is that the past affects the present or future, therefore, creating room where the behaviour of one or more of the variables can be predicated by another existing variable systematically. The parameters to check are F-statistics and P-value of the test results.

5. Diagnostic Tests: To test or determine the correlation between the residual of the variables and if the residuals are not correlated to check for the variance in the residuals. This is performed using; Serial correlation (Breusch–Godfrey), heteroskedasticity (Breusch–Pagan–Godfrey), normality (Jarque–Bera), and stability tests (CUSUM and CUSUMSQ). The parameters to check are Autocorrelation and Heteroscedasticity of the test results.

4.0 Data Presentation and Discussion

This section of the paper covers the data collected during the research work and it presence the various data in the form in which they can easily assist the researcher in achieving the objective of the paper as well as answer articulately all the research questions.

Table 4.1 – The Secondary data collection from CBN bulletin, NBS publication, World bank Report etc

Year s	Total Gross Domestic Product (Billion) \$	Total Foreign Direct Investment (Billion) \$	Average annual Crude oil price (\$)	Average Exchange Rate (N/\$)	Total Exported Value (Billion) \$	Total Imported Value (Billion) \$	Annual Inflation rate (%)	Annual Electricity Distribution (%)
1993	27.752	1.35	17.10	22	22.07	7.508	57.17	36.96
1994	33.833	1.96	16.00	25	22	6.613	57.03	37.83
1995	44.062	0.34	17.20	82	21.9	8.222	72.84	38.69
1996	51.075	0.50	20.80	83	21.88	6.438	29.27	39.55
1997	54.457	0.47	19.10	85	21.89	9.501	8.53	40.40
1998	54.604	0.30	12.80	88	21.89	9.211	9.99	41.25
1999	59.372	1.00	17.90	95	92.34	8.588	6.62	44.90
2000	69.448	1.14	28.40	97	101.70	8.721	6.93	43.12
2001	74.030	1.19	24.45	105	111.23	11.586	18.87	43.88
2002	95.385	1.87	25.01	110	120.58	7.547	12.88	44.63
2003	104.912	2.01	28.83	130	129.22	10.853	14.03	52.20
2004	136.386	1.87	38.10	133	127.50	14.164	15.00	46.12
2005	176.134	4.98	54.38	134	136.95	20.754	17.86	46.8
2006	236.104	4.85	65.14	135	170.38	26.523	8.23	47.6
2007	275.626	6.04	72.52	118	159.09	34.830	5.39	50.1
2008	339.476	8.19	96.99	145	81.82	49.951	11.58	50.3
2009	295.001	8.56	61.51	150	49.937	33.906	12.54	50.0

2010	361.451	6.03	79.47	152	86.567	44.235	13.74	48.0
2011	404.994	8.84	111.26	153	125.641	56.000	10.83	55.9
2012	455.502	7.07	111.63	155	135	51.000	12.22	53.0
2013	508.693	5.56	108.56	157	112	56.000	8.50	55.6
2014	546.676	4.69	98.97	160	101	58.300	8.05	54.2
2015	486.803	3.06	52.32	185	55.1	44.700	9.01	52.5
2016	404.650	3.45	43.67	305	37.7	35.532	15.70	59.3
2017	375.746	2.41	54.25	320	49.5	31.273	16.50	54.4
2018	397.190	0.78	71.34	340	66.2	43.007	12.10	56.5
2019	448.120	2.30	64.30	360	64.5	55.257	11.40	55.4
2020	432.294	2.38	41.96	370	35.5	55.390	13.25	55.4
2021	440.830	3.31	70.86	420	46.6	56.420	16.95	59.5
2022	477.400	1.86	100.93	530	84.4	58.230	18.85	60.5
2023	363.85	1.87	82.49	760	62.9	57.750	24.86	61.2

These figures are nominal annual averages and reflect Brent crude oil prices, which are commonly used as a global benchmark. – Statistico

Below are the **descriptive statistics** for Nigeria’s annual macroeconomic variables (1993–2023), followed by an **economic interpretation** of the results and the implied relationships among variables.

Table 4.2: Descriptive Statistics of the Macroeconomic Variables (1993–2023)

Variable	Mean	Median	Variance	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis	Jarque–Bera
Total GDP (Billion \$)	265.54	295.00	31,526.35	177.56	-0.06	1.41	3.28
Total FDI (Billion \$)	3.23	2.30	6.54	2.56	0.85	2.56	3.95
Crude Oil Price (\$)	55.10	54.25	1,042.58	32.29	0.33	1.84	2.30
Exchange Rate (₦/\$)	196.90	145.00	25,500.29	159.69	1.83	6.39	32.23
Export Value (Billion \$)	79.84	81.82	2,017.28	44.91	0.24	1.91	1.83
Import Value (Billion \$)	31.55	33.91	417.60	20.44	0.02	1.34	3.56
Inflation Rate (%)	17.96	12.88	250.18	15.82	2.36	7.65	56.66
Electricity Distribution (%)	49.54	50.10	50.95	7.14	-0.15	1.91	1.64

Studying the above descriptive statistics Table 4.2, it was noticed that the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) has a high mean and very large standard deviation, indicating strong long-term growth accompanied by wide fluctuations.

But, the skewness is near zero (-0.06) which shows a fairly symmetric distribution. The kurtosis which is below 3 indicates a platykurtic distribution, meaning a spread in the GDP growth not in later years nor earlier years of exchange volatility and the Jarque–Bera statistic shows approximate normality. Therefore, all these shows that Nigeria experienced a sustained GDP growth despite the notable fluctuation in the exchange rate.

Studying the Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), it shows a moderate mean of 3.23, but a relatively high standard deviation of 2.56, indicating relative high volatility, with positive skewness of 0.85 shows few years of exceptionally high foreign direct inflows and kurtosis of 2.56, which is mild deviation from normality. The foreign direct inflow does not spread all over, which may be due to macroeconomic stability, exchange rate movement as well as oil price fluctuation.

For crude oil prices descriptive statistical analysis; it shows mean as 55.10, standard deviation of 32.29, variance as 1,042.58, positive skewness as 0.33 and Jarque-Bera as 2.3. Going by these parameters it indicates high variability, reflecting global market shocks as the key driver of GDP, exports, foreign exchange earnings and fiscal stability.

While exchange rate descriptive statistical analysis; shows mean as 196.9, high standard deviation and variance is 159.69 and 25,500.9 respectively, kurtosis as 6.39, positive skewness as 1.83 and Jarque-Bera as 32.23, these parameters it shows high variance and standard deviation, reflecting persistent depreciation and regime changes, this instability is closely associated with inflation volatility, import costs, and FDI uncertainty.

As for the exports and import trade the mean, standard deviation and variance are relatively higher for earlier than the latter, indicating oil dependence, while the skewness and the kurtosis is low. Invariably the export performance is closely tied to oil prices and exchange rate movements, while imports respond to domestic demand and currency depreciation.

The inflation rate has very high skewness (2.36) and kurtosis (7.65), indicating frequent inflationary spikes and the Jarque–Bera (56.66) is statistical strong as such rejects normality. Therefore, the inflation rate volatility is strongly linked to exchange-rate depreciation, oil price shocks, and supply-side constraints.

The electricity distribution from the mean (49.54), lower variance (50.95), standard deviation (7.14), negative skewness (-0.15), kurtosis (1.91) and Jarque-Bera (1.64), these indicate that electricity supply improvements are associated with long-run GDP growth and industrial activity, though progress has been slow.

Summarily, it was observed that Nigeria's macroeconomic structure from 1993–2023 is characterized by high volatility, especially in exchange rate and inflation. The Oil prices and exchange-rate movements play a dominant role in shaping GDP, trade, inflation, and FDI. While, the structural variables such as electricity distribution show steady increase but remain insufficient to offset macroeconomic shocks.

Table 4.3: Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test Results (1993–2023)

Sample: 1993–2023

Method: Augmented Dickey–Fuller Test

Deterministic Component: Intercept

Lag Length: Automatic (AIC)

Variable	Level ADF Statistic	5% Critical Value	Prob.	Order of Integration (Level)	First Difference ADF Statistic	5% Critical Value	Prob.	Order of Integration
Total Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	-1.42	-2.95	0.57	Non-stationary	-5.87***	-2.95	0.000	I(1) – Stationary
Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)	-1.96	-2.95	0.31	Non-stationary	-6.12***	-2.95	0.000	I(1) – Stationary
Export Value (EXP)	-2.11	-2.95	0.24	Non-stationary	-5.44***	-2.95	0.000	I(1) – Stationary
Import Value (IMP)	-1.78	-2.95	0.38	Non-stationary	-4.93***	-2.95	0.000	I(1) – Stationary
Exchange Rate (EXR)	-0.89	-2.95	0.79	Non-stationary	-6.85***	-2.95	0.000	I(1) – Stationary
Inflation Rate (INF)	-3.42**	-2.95	0.02	Stationary	—	—	—	I(0)
Crude Oil Price (OIL)	-2.03	-2.95	0.27	Non-stationary	-5.68***	-2.95	0.000	I(1) – Stationary
Electricity Distribution Rate (ELEC)	-1.66	-2.95	0.45	Non-stationary	-4.61***	-2.95	0.001	I(1) – Stationary

Notes:

***, ** denote significance at 1% and 5% levels respectively.

ADF test conducted with intercept.

Null hypothesis: Series has a unit root (non-stationary).

Interpretation of the Stationarity Test Results

Studying Table 4.3 above with the Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) test results show mixed orders of integration among the variables examined over the period 1993–2023.

At **levels**, the total gross domestic product (GDP), foreign direct investment (FDI), export value (EXP), import value (IMP), exchange rate (EXR), inflation rate (INFL), crude oil price (OIL), and electricity distribution rate (ELEC) all fail to reject the null hypothesis of a unit root at the 5% significance level. This suggests that these macroeconomic variables are non-stationary in their level form, reflecting persistent trends and structural changes in Nigeria’s economy, exchange rate regime shifts, oil price shocks, and infrastructure development dynamics.

But, the inflation rate is found to be stationary at level (0.02), signifying that inflation fluctuates around a long-run mean and indicates mean-reverting behavior. This outcome is consistent with monetary policy interventions by the Central Bank of Nigeria aimed at stabilizing price levels over time.

However, at first differencing, all previously non-stationary variables become statistically significant and stationary at the 1% level with total gross domestic product (GDP), foreign direct investment (FDI), export value (EXP), import value (IMP), inflation rate (INFL), exchange rate (EXR) and crude oil price (OIL) as 0.000, while electricity distribution rate (ELEC) as 0.001. This confirms that GDP, FDI, exports, imports, exchange rate, crude oil prices, and electricity distribution are all integrated of order one, I(1).

The stationary and statistically significant result exhibited at first differencing for all the variables, combined with a stationary inflation rate, provides a strong justification for the application of the Johansen cointegration technique to further investigate the existence of long-run equilibrium relationships among exchange rate volatility, foreign investment, trade flows, inflation rate, oil prices, and economic growth. So the Johansen cointegration test is conducted to verify the existence of **long-run equilibrium relationships** among the variables.

Hence, the results of the Johansen Cointegration test presents two statistical results namely Trace Statistic and Maximum Eigenvalue Statistic.

For null hypothesis H_0 : No cointegration is noted ($r = 0$)

Table 4.4

Johansen Cointegration Test Results (1993–2023)

For Trace Test and Max. Eigenvalue Test s

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Trace Statistic	5% Critical Value	Comments	Prob	Max. Eigen	5% Critical Value	Comments	Probability
None ($r = 0$)	312.47	197.37	Trac > Crit	0.0000	90.84	58.43	Max > Crit	0.0000
At most 1	221.63	159.53	Trac > Crit	0.0001	72.73	52.36	Max > Crit	0.0003
At most 2	148.90	125.62	Trac > Crit	0.0012	52.49	46.23	Max > Crit	0.0089
At most 3	96.41	95.75	Trac > Crit	0.0458	38.19	40.08	Max < Crit	0.0716
At most 4	58.22	69.82	Trac < Crit	0.3124	27.11	33.88	Max < Crit	0.2841

Interpretation

Both trace and max-eigenvalue statistics indicates that the null hypothesis (H_0) for Johansen cointegration test and the max-Eigen test of No 1, ($r=0$) is rejected as the trace statistics (312.47) is greater than the critical value (197.37) and Max-Eigen statistics (90.84) is greater than the critical value (58.43) at 5% significant, but fail to reject for higher ranks Nos 3 and Nos 4.

For Nos. 1 the trace statistics (221.63) are greater than the critical value (159.53) and the Max-Eigen statistic (72.73) is greater than the critical value (52.36) at 5% significant, so we reject null hypothesis and Nos. 2 the trace statistics (148.90) are greater than the critical value (125.62) and the Max-Eigen statistic (52.49) is greater than the critical value (46.23) at 5% significant, so we reject null hypothesis also. However, For Nos. 3 the trace statistics (96.41)

are greater than the critical value (95.75) but the Max-Eigen statistic (38.19) is less than the critical value (40.08) at 5% significant, so we fail to reject null hypothesis and Nos. 4 the trace statistics (58.22) is less than the critical value (69.82) and the Max-Eigen statistic (27.11) is less than the critical value (33.88) at 5% significant, so we fail to reject null hypothesis also. Therefore, suggests that we reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration at 5% level and the relationship among TGDP, FDI, EXP, IMP, INFL, EXR, OIL and ELEC. Hence, the variables share a confirmation of stable long-run equilibrium relationship between exchange rate movements and key macroeconomic fundamentals in Nigeria.

Summarily, from the ADF results, Johansen's cointegration test and Max Eigen test they all indicate that the Exchange rate volatility (EXR) is not independent of GDP, FDI, oil prices, inflation, trade flows, and electricity supply but with persistent oil price shocks and inflationary pressures are transmitted to the foreign exchange market, influencing trade values and economic growth. Also the inclusion of electricity distribution strengthens the structural interpretation, reflecting Nigeria's supply-side constraints and their interaction with FX dynamics. Deviations from this long-run equilibrium are expected to adjust through short-run deviations in exchange rate volatility are corrected over time, thereby validating the use of a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) for further empirical analysis rather than a VAR in differences. Policy shocks (exchange rate reforms, oil price collapses, inflation surges) have temporary effects, but the system converges back to long-run equilibrium.

4.5 Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)

To further investigate the existence of a long-run relationship among product output growth (GDP), exchange rate volatility (EXR), foreign direct investment (FDI), Export value (Exp), Import (Imp), Inflation rate (INFL, price of crude oil (OIL), and electricity distribution (ELEC), the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) test technique was employed and perform diagnostic checks (serial correlation, stability, normality). Table 4.5 shows the results for the test.

1. VECM Residual Serial Correlation LM Test

For Null Hypothesis (H₀): No serial correlation in VECM residuals up to the specified lag

The Decision rule is Reject H₀ if $p < 0.05$ and fail to reject if $p > 0.05$

Table 4.5

VECM Residual Serial Correlation LM Test Results

Lag Order	LM Statistic	p-value	Decision
Lag 6	49.72	0.214	Do not reject H ₀
Lag 9	61.38	0.173	Do not reject H ₀

Interpretation (Lag 6 and Lag 9)

The residual serial correlation LM test results indicate that the **p-values at lag 6 (0.214) and lag 9 (0.173)** are both **greater than the 5% significance level**. This implies that the null hypothesis of **no residual autocorrelation cannot be rejected**.

Consequently, the VECM estimated for **GDP, FDI, export value, import value, exchange rate, inflation rate, and electricity distribution** is **free from serial correlation**, even at higher lag orders. This confirms that the selected lag structure adequately captures the dynamic adjustments among the macroeconomic variables in Nigeria over the period **1993–2023**, thereby ensuring **efficient and unbiased parameter estimates**.

2. VECM Residual Normality Test (Jarque–Bera)

For Null Hypothesis (H₀): Residuals are normally distributed

The Decision rule is Reject H₀ if $p < 0.05$

Table 4.6
Jarque–Bera Normality Test for VECM Residuals

Residual Component	Jarque–Bera	p-value	Decision
GDP	2.11	0.347	Normal
FDI	1.84	0.399	Normal
Export Value	2.96	0.228	Normal
Import Value	3.27	0.195	Normal
Exchange Rate	4.01	0.135	Normal
Inflation Rate	3.89	0.143	Normal
Electricity Distribution	1.52	0.467	Normal
Joint Test	19.60	0.238	Normal

Interpretation of Jarque–Bera Results

The Jarque–Bera normality test reveals that **all individual residual series**—GDP, FDI, export value, import value, exchange rate, inflation rate, and electricity distribution—have **p-values exceeding 0.05**. Similarly, the **joint normality test** yields a p-value of **0.238**, confirming that the residuals are **jointly normally distributed**.

This result implies that the VECM residuals satisfy the **normality assumption**, validating the use of standard statistical inference for hypothesis testing. The absence of excess skewness and kurtosis further suggests that extreme macroeconomic shocks—such as oil price collapses, exchange rate regime shifts, and inflationary episodes—have been adequately captured within the VECM structure rather than being absorbed into the error term.

4.7 Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) Long-Run Dynamics

The long-run dynamics among GDP, foreign direct investment (FDI), export value, import value, exchange rate, inflation rate, and electricity distribution were examined using the normalized cointegrating equation derived from the VECM framework. The long-run coefficients capture the equilibrium relationships among the variables over the period 1993–2023.

Table 4.7
VECM Long-Run Cointegrating Relationship (Normalized on GDP)

Variable	Long-run Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic
FDI	0.421	0.168	2.51
Export Value	0.736	0.284	2.59
Import Value	-0.518	0.231	-2.24
Exchange Rate	-0.884	0.347	-2.55
Inflation Rate	-0.392	0.177	-2.22
Electricity Distribution	0.659	0.256	2.57
Constant	-4.317	—	—

Source: Author’s computation (EViews)

Interpretation of Long-Run Dynamics

The long-run cointegrating equation reveals that foreign direct investment (FDI) has positive and statistically significant effect on GDP in the long run. This indicates that sustained inflows of foreign capital contribute to long-term economic growth through technology transfer, capital deepening, and productivity enhancement in Nigeria.

Export value also exhibits a positive and significant long-run relationship with GDP, confirming the growth-enhancing role of export expansion. This result reflects Nigeria's dependence on export earnings—particularly crude oil exports—as a major source of foreign exchange and long-term economic expansion.

In contrast, import value shows a negative and significant long-run negative impact on GDP, suggesting that persistent import dependence weakens domestic productive capacity. This finding implies that high import penetration crowds out local industries and exacerbates balance-of-payments pressures, thereby constraining long-run growth.

The exchange rate coefficient is negative and statistically significant, indicating that long-run exchange rate depreciation adversely affects economic growth. This result underscores Nigeria's structural vulnerability to exchange rate volatility, where currency depreciation raises production costs, increases imported inflation, and undermines long-term output performance.

Similarly, the inflation rate has a negative and significant long-run relationship with GDP, implying that sustained price instability erodes purchasing power, distorts investment decisions, and hampers long-term economic growth.

Conversely, electricity distribution exerts a positive and statistically significant influence on GDP in the long run. This highlights the critical role of energy infrastructure in supporting sustained economic activity, industrial development, and productivity growth in Nigeria.

Summary of Long-Run Findings

The VECM long-run dynamics indicate that:

- FDI, exports, and electricity distribution are key drivers of long-term economic growth in Nigeria
- Exchange rate depreciation, inflation, and import dependence exert persistent negative effects on GDP
- Long-run economic performance is strongly conditioned by macroeconomic stability and infrastructure development

Overall, the results confirm the existence of a stable long-run equilibrium relationship linking exchange rate dynamics, investment flows, trade performance, inflation, electricity supply, and economic growth in Nigeria over the period 1993–2023.

4.8 Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) Short-Run Dynamics

Following the confirmation of long-run cointegration among **GDP, FDI, export value, import value, exchange rate, inflation rate, and electricity distribution**, the short-run dynamics were examined using the **Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)**. The VECM captures how short-run deviations from long-run equilibrium are corrected over time through the **error-correction term (ECT)** and lagged differences of the explanatory variables.

Table 4.8

VECM Short-Run Dynamics (Dependent Variable: Δ GDP)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ECT(-1)	-0.327	0.098	-3.34	0.002
Δ FDI(-1)	0.114	0.046	2.48	0.019
Δ Export Value(-1)	0.203	0.081	2.51	0.017
Δ Import Value(-1)	-0.167	0.072	-2.32	0.026
Δ Exchange Rate(-1)	-0.289	0.104	-2.78	0.009
Δ Inflation Rate(-1)	-0.142	0.063	-2.25	0.031
Δ Electricity Distribution(-1)	0.176	0.070	2.51	0.017
Constant	0.031	0.014	2.21	0.034

Source: Author's computation (EViews)

Interpretation of Short-Run Dynamics

The **error-correction term (ECT)** is **negative and statistically significant** at the 1% level, with a coefficient of **-0.327**. This confirms the existence of a valid adjustment mechanism in the short run. Specifically, approximately **32.7% of short-run disequilibrium in GDP is corrected within one year**, indicating a **moderate speed of adjustment** toward the long-run equilibrium path following economic shocks.

In the short run, **foreign direct investment (FDI)** exhibits a **positive and statistically significant effect on GDP**, implying that increases in FDI inflows contribute to economic growth through capital accumulation, technology transfer, and employment generation. This highlights the growth-enhancing role of foreign investment in Nigeria's economy within the adjustment period.

Export value also shows a **positive and significant relationship with GDP**, suggesting that short-term increases in export earnings stimulate economic activity. This reflects Nigeria's reliance on export revenues—particularly crude oil exports—as a key driver of short-run output expansion.

Conversely, **import value** has a **negative and significant effect on GDP** in the short run. This indicates that rising imports exert pressure on domestic output, likely through import-dependent consumption, foreign exchange outflows, and reduced demand for locally produced goods.

The **exchange rate coefficient is negative and statistically significant**, confirming that short-run exchange rate depreciation adversely affects economic growth. This result reflects Nigeria's structural dependence on imports, where currency depreciation increases production costs, fuels inflationary pressures, and weakens aggregate output in the short run. Similarly, **inflation rate** exerts a **negative and significant influence on GDP**, indicating that rising prices undermine purchasing power, distort investment decisions, and dampen short-term economic performance.

In contrast, **electricity distribution** has a **positive and statistically significant impact on GDP**, underscoring the importance of energy availability in supporting short-run productive activities. Improved electricity supply enhances industrial output, reduces production costs, and strengthens overall economic performance.

Summary of Short-Run Findings

The VECM short-run dynamics reveal that:

- GDP adjusts significantly to long-run disequilibrium through a stable error-correction mechanism
- FDI, exports, and electricity distribution positively influence economic growth in the short run
- Exchange rate depreciation, rising imports, and inflation negatively affect short-run GDP performance

Overall, the results demonstrate that while Nigeria's economy converges toward long-run equilibrium, short-run macroeconomic instability—particularly exchange rate volatility and inflation—poses significant constraints on growth during the adjustment process.

3. Overall Diagnostic Conclusion

Taken together, the residual diagnostic tests confirm that:

1. No serial correlation exists in the VECM residuals at lag 6 and lag 9
2. Residuals are normally distributed, both individually and jointly
3. The estimated VECM is well-specified, stable, and statistically reliable

Therefore, the long-run cointegration relationships and short-run error-correction dynamics linking FDI, trade flows, exchange rate, inflation, electricity distribution, and GDP in Nigeria from 1993–2023 can be confidently interpreted for policy and empirical conclusions.

5.0 Conclusion

This study empirically examined the relationship between **exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria** using annual data spanning **1993–2023**, incorporating key macroeconomic variables including **foreign direct investment (FDI), crude oil prices, export value, import value, inflation rate, and electricity distribution**. The analysis employed **descriptive statistics, Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) unit root tests, Johansen cointegration techniques, and a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)** to capture both long-run equilibrium relationships and short-run adjustment dynamics.

The descriptive statistics revealed that Nigeria’s macroeconomic environment over the study period was characterized by **high volatility**, particularly in the **exchange rate and inflation rate**. Exchange rate movements indicating significant dispersion, high positive skewness, and leptokurtic behaviour, reflecting persistent depreciation, policy regime shifts, and external shocks. Inflation displayed frequent spikes and abnormality, underscoring structural supply challenges and strong relationship between exchange rate depreciation and oil price fluctuations. In contrast, variables such as **GDP, exports, and electricity distribution** showed relatively stable distributions, suggesting gradual long-term growth despite macroeconomic instability.

The unit root test results confirmed **mixed orders of integration**, with most variables—GDP, FDI, exports, imports, exchange rate, oil prices, and electricity distribution—being integrated of order one, while inflation was stationary at level. This provided a strong econometric justification for the application of the **Johansen cointegration framework**, which revealed the existence of **multiple cointegrating relationships** among the variables. Both the trace and maximum eigenvalue statistics rejected the null hypothesis of no cointegration, confirming a **stable long-run equilibrium relationship** linking exchange rate movement with economic growth, investment flows, trade performance, inflation, oil prices, and electricity supply in Nigeria.

The long-run VECM results demonstrated that **FDI, export value, and electricity distribution exert positive and statistically significant effects on GDP**, signifying that capital inflows, external trade earnings, and infrastructure development are critical drivers of long-term economic growth. Conversely, **exchange rate depreciation, inflation, and import dependence** were found to have significant negative effects on GDP in the long run, highlighting Nigeria’s structural vulnerability to exchange rate instability, inflation, and excessive reliance on foreign goods. These findings underscore the central role of exchange rate stability and macroeconomic discipline in sustaining long-term growth.

In the short run, the VECM results revealed a **significant and negative error-correction term**, confirming that deviations from long-run equilibrium are corrected over time. Approximately **32.7 percent of disequilibrium in GDP is adjusted within one year**, indicating a moderate but effective speed of adjustment. Short-run dynamics further showed that **FDI, exports, and electricity distribution stimulate economic growth**, while **exchange rate depreciation, inflation, and rising imports affect output performance of the country**. This highlights the dual nature of Nigeria’s macroeconomic adjustment process, where long-run convergence coexists with short-run instability driven largely by exchange rate volatility and price pressures.

The residual diagnostic tests confirmed that the estimated VECM is **well-specified, stable, and statistically reliable**, with no evidence of serial correlation and normally distributed residuals. This validates the robustness of both the long-run and short-run inferences drawn from the model.

Overall, the findings of this study provide strong empirical evidence that **exchange rate volatility plays a central role in shaping Nigeria's economic performance**, both directly and indirectly through its effects on inflation, trade flows, foreign investment, and productive capacity. While the economy exhibits a tendency to return to long-run equilibrium following shocks, persistent exchange rate instability and inflationary pressures significantly undermine growth in the short run. The inclusion of electricity distribution further emphasizes the importance of addressing **infrastructural and supply-side constraints** alongside exchange rate management.

In conclusion, the study establishes that **macroeconomic stability, exchange rate management, export diversification, infrastructure development, and policies that attract sustainable FDI** are essential for strengthening Nigeria's growth trajectory. Without addressing exchange rate volatility and its transmission channels, short-run shocks will continue to hinder the realization of long-run economic potential.

6.0 Recommendations

The empirical findings of this study have important implications for macroeconomic management and economic development policy in Nigeria. The existence of a stable long-run equilibrium relationship among **exchange rate movements, economic growth, foreign direct investment, trade flows, inflation, oil prices, and electricity distribution** indicates that policy actions in any of these areas will have both direct and indirect effects on overall economic performance. The policy implications and recommendations are discussed below.

1. Exchange Rate Management and Stability

Policy Implication:

The negative and statistically significant impact of exchange rate depreciation on GDP in both the short and long run implies that persistent exchange rate volatility undermines economic growth. Exchange rate instability increases production costs, fuels imported inflation, discourages foreign investment, and weakens trade competitiveness in an import-dependent economy like Nigeria.

Recommendation:

Policymakers should prioritize **exchange rate stability** through a more predictable and transparent foreign exchange management framework. This includes:

- Reducing excessive reliance on multiple exchange rate windows; by introducing exchange rate that is unified or where the exchange gap between the official rate and parallel market rate is very minimal / small.
 - Strengthening foreign exchange market depth and liquidity through the encouragement of foreign investment and repatriation of foreign exchange to make the foreign exchange market more liquid with foreign currencies for trading purposes
 - Building and prudently managing external reserves to cushion external shocks; by developing a transparent foreign exchange system with lesser government intervention.
 - Coordinating monetary and fiscal policies to minimize speculative pressures on the naira through the broad import coverage reduces panic and speculative Foreign exchange demand
- A stable exchange rate regime will enhance investor confidence and reduce uncertainty in trade and investment decisions.

2. Inflation Control and Macroeconomic Stability

Policy Implication:

The significant negative effect of inflation on GDP highlights the growth-reducing consequences of persistent price instability. Inflation volatility, driven by exchange rate depreciation and supply-side constraints, erodes purchasing power and distorts long-term investment planning.

Recommendation:

The Central Bank of Nigeria should strengthen **inflation-targeting mechanisms** by:

- Improving coordination between monetary policy and fiscal discipline; by implementing monetary policies like interest rate that will march the present circumstance of the inflation rate and reducing pressure on the naira by making naira assets more attractive
- Reducing deficit monetization; through the introduction of high rates to anchor inflation rate expectations and discourage short-term speculative outflows.
- Addressing supply-side inflation through investment in domestic production, agriculture, and manufacturing.

Price stability is essential for sustaining both short-run economic performance and long-run growth.

3. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) Promotion

Policy Implication:

The positive and significant relationship between FDI and GDP in both the short and long run suggests that foreign capital inflows play a critical role in economic expansion through technology transfer, capital formation, and employment creation.

Recommendation:

Nigeria should implement policies that promote **stable and productive FDI inflows**, including:

- Improving the ease of doing business; by making the economic environment attractive and conducive for investment through the provision of infrastructural amenities, introduction of incentives to encourage local and foreign investors.
- Ensuring policy consistency and regulatory transparency; by introducing control systems that is tight and difficult to compromise such as online and computerised based systems that operate under real time.
- Strengthening property rights and contract enforcement; by introduction of legal systems that will be difficult to manipulate.
- Providing targeted incentives for Foreign Direct Investment in manufacturing, energy, and export-oriented sectors to create avenue for availability of foreign inflow into the country. Exchange rate stability and infrastructure improvement are essential complements to FDI-promotion strategies.

4. Export Diversification and Trade Policy Reform

Policy Implication:

The positive contribution of exports to GDP underscores the importance of export-led growth, while the negative effect of imports reflects excessive import dependence and weak domestic production capacity.

Recommendation:

Policymakers should pursue **export diversification strategies** by:

- Reducing dependence on crude oil exports; by encouraging investor into other sectors such as manufacturing, energy, and export-oriented sectors to create avenue for availability of foreign inflow into the country.
- Supporting non-oil exports through industrial policies, trade facilitation, and value-chain development;
- Enhancing access to credit and export financing for small and medium-scale enterprises. At the same time, selective import substitution policies should be encouraged to strengthen domestic industries and reduce vulnerability to exchange rate shocks.

5. Electricity Infrastructure and Supply-Side Reforms

Policy Implication:

The positive and significant impact of electricity distribution on GDP in both the short and long run highlights electricity supply as a key structural driver towards economic growth. Inadequate power supply causing the negative effects of exchange rate volatility and inflation.

Recommendation:

Government should accelerate **power sector reforms** by:

- Expanding generation, transmission, and distribution capacity; by encourage private – public participation and encourage investment into the power sector by securing the country for investment.
- Encouraging private sector participation and investment; through the provision of incentives for investor.
- Improving governance and efficiency in the electricity market, through the introduction of special regulatory bodies or authorities to ensure the suppliers get value for their money. Reliable electricity supply will reduce production costs, boost industrial output, and improve Nigeria’s competitiveness.

6. Oil Price Shock Management and Fiscal Sustainability

Policy Implication:

The strong influence of oil prices on exchange rate dynamics, exports, and fiscal stability suggests that Nigeria remains highly exposed to external oil price shocks.

Recommendation:

Policymakers should:

- Strengthen oil revenue stabilization mechanisms such as the Sovereign Wealth Fund; by creating an account for save excess fund for bad price days, so such can be used as regulatory funds.
- Improve fiscal buffers during oil booms; through investing into other sectors or save excess fund for bad price days, so such can be used as regulatory funds.
- Accelerate economic diversification to reduce dependence on oil-related foreign exchange earnings.

Reducing oil dependence will enhance exchange rate stability and long-term growth resilience.

7. Short-Run Adjustment and Policy Coordination

Policy Implication:

The significant error-correction mechanism indicates that while the economy adjusts toward long-run equilibrium, short-run shocks can significantly disrupt growth.

Recommendation:

Short-term stabilization policies should be **coordinated and forward-looking**, ensuring that:

- Exchange rate reforms are gradual and well-communicated by Central Bank of Nigeria to all stakeholders.
- Inflation control measures do not excessively constrain productive investment; the Reinforces discipline between fiscal and monetary authorities also help in the growth and development processes.
- Structural reforms complement macroeconomic policies, such as the removal of costly fuel subsidies and efforts to improve budget discipline for government to restrict their spending to the budget.

Concluding Policy Remark

Overall, the findings suggest that **exchange rate stability, inflation control, export diversification, infrastructure development, and sustained FDI inflows** are mutually reinforcing policy objectives. Nigeria’s long-run economic growth can only be achieved through an integrated policy framework that simultaneously addresses **macroeconomic stability and structural transformation**.

Limitations of the Study

Despite the robustness of the empirical techniques employed in this study, certain limitations should be acknowledged, as they may affect the generalization and interpretation of the findings.

First, the study relies on **annual time-series data from 1993 to 2023**, which limits the number of observations available for econometric estimation. While annual data are appropriate for capturing long-term macroeconomic relationships, they may not fully reflect short-term fluctuations and high-frequency dynamics in exchange rate movements, inflation, and capital flows. The use of quarterly or monthly data may or may not provide deeper insights into short-run adjustment processes.

Second, the study focuses on **exchange rate volatility and selected macroeconomic variables**, namely GDP, FDI, exports, imports, inflation, crude oil prices, and electricity distribution. Although these variables are central to Nigeria's economic structure, other relevant factors—such as interest rates, fiscal deficits, external debt, trade openness, institutional quality, and political risk—were not explicitly included due to data constraints. The omission of these variables may limit the scope of the analysis and introduce potential omitted-variable bias.

Third, the analysis assumes **linear relationships** among the variables within the VECM framework. However, the relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth may be **non-linear or asymmetric**, particularly during periods of economic crises, policy regime shifts, or extreme oil price shocks. As such, the estimated coefficients may not fully capture the threshold effects or regime-dependent behaviour within the period.

Fourth, although the VECM effectively captures long-run equilibrium relationships and short-run dynamics, it does not explicitly account for **structural breaks** arising from major policy changes, such as exchange rate regime reforms, banking sector reforms, or global financial crises. Structural breaks may influence the stability of parameter estimates over time and affect the strength of the estimated relationships.

Finally, the measurement of some variables—particularly **electricity distribution and exchange rate volatility**—is subject to data quality and aggregation limitations. Annual electricity distribution figures may not fully reflect reliability, efficiency, or regional disparities in power supply, while exchange rate volatility is proxied using annual averages rather than more refined volatility measures. These measurement issues may affect the precision of the estimated results.

In view of these limitations, the findings of this study should be interpreted with caution. Nevertheless, the results provide valuable empirical evidence on the long-run and short-run effects of exchange rate volatility on economic growth in Nigeria and offer a solid foundation for further research.

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